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***Typhaeus bubeniki* sp. nov. (Coleoptera: Geotrupidae)
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Abstract

A new species of the genus *Typhaeus* Leach, 1815, *Typhaeus bubeniki* sp. nov., is described and illustrated from the Spanish region of Murcia in the vicinity of Cañada de la Cruz. The new species is compared to the most similar *Typhaeus typhoeus* (Linnaeus, 1758), based on *Scarabaeus typhoeus*. Illustrations in colour photographs, results of DNA analyses and maps of distribution for both species are presented. A lectotype of *Scarabaeus typhoeus* (designated by Landin 1956) is also illustrated.

Keywords: taxonomy, new species, Coleoptera, Geotrupidae, *Typhaeus*, Murcia, Spain, Palaearctic region

Introduction

In March 2022 and subsequently in March 2023 and 2025, members of the International Entomological Association – Nature Conservation, conducted a survey of insect biodiversity in the Murcia region of Spain within a 50 km radius of the village of Cañada de la Cruz. This resulted in the discovery of a different species of the genus *Typhaeus* Leach, 1815. Detailed examinations of the morphology and genitalia and subsequent DNA analyses have revealed that it represents a new species clearly differing from the diagnostic characters of *Typhaeus typhoeus* (Linnaeus, 1758) which occurs in Europe and North Africa. It should be noted here that the occurrence of *T. typhoeus* in the Czech Republic is limited only to the area near the village of Hřensko, not far from the German border. Its occurrence in Moravia (Czech Republic) and neighbouring Slovakia has not been confirmed.

The biology of *T. typhoeus* was described in detail by Brussaard (1983); the behaviour of females by Fremlin (2017) and feeding preferences by Turner (2023).

Material and methods

Colour photographs of the habitus and diagnostic features were taken with a Nikon D850 digital camera with a 90 mm macro lens using Adobe Photoshop and Helicon Focus software. Photographs of the genitals were taken with a Nikon D850 camera with a Mitutoyo 10× lens with Rainox auxiliary lenses (for the author of the photographs see "Acknowledgements" below).

Methods of genetic analysis. DNA isolation, PCR, gel electrophoresis, Sanger sequencing. For the genetic sequence comparison with the detected difference 1.95% in COI barcoding area between *Typhaeus typhoeus* and *T. bubeniki* sp. nov. see Fig. 7.

Collection abbreviations

BBFM Collection of Boris Bubeník, Frýdek-Místek, Silesia, Czech Republic;

AWHS Collection of Antonín Wrzecionko, Horní Suchá, Silesia, Czech Republic;

LINN Linnean Society of London, GB;
NMPC Museum of the Czech Republic, Prague, Czech Republic.

TAXONOMY

Typhaeus bubeniki sp. nov.

lsid:zoobank.org:pub:387E5FD5-1F86-409A-B1F5-3548561BECC4

Type locality. Spain, Murcia, Cañada de la Cruz, 1550 m.

Type material. Holotype, ♂, labelled: “19.3.2022 / España-R.Murcia 1550m / Cañada de la Cruz-env. / leg. Bubeník and Wrzecionko” [printed] // “HOLOTYPE / *Typhaeus bubeniki* sp. nov. / det. A. Wrzecionko 2025” [red label, printed]. **Paratypes**. 12 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, with the same locality label as in holotype; 15 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀ with same locality label except for: “14.3.2025”. All paratypes labelled: “PARATYPE / *Typhaeus bubeniki* sp. nov. / det. A. Wrzecionko 2025”. Total number of paratypes 35.

Type depository. Holotype in AWHS, 17 paratypes in BBFM; 16 paratypes in AWHS and one pair of paratypes in NMPC.

Description of the male holotype. Body length 19 mm. The body is convex, black and very shiny. This species exhibits sexual dimorphism.

Head (Fig. 2, 1) elongated, conical in shape and with a rounded frons. The spikes on the sides above the eyes are sharp.

Labrum (Fig. 2, 1) transverse with rounded lateral margins and truncate, almost flat anterior margin, surface dotted with punctures and foveae and anterior margin is densely rusty setose.

Frons, vertex and clypeus (Fig. 2, 1; Fig. 3, 1). The vertex is dilated from its basal portion towards distinct lateromedian horn-like edges and attenuated anteriorly towards arcuate anterior clypeal margin edge. There are smaller pits and numerous small punctures on the surface.

Pronotum (Fig. 1, 2) is 10 mm wide and the 4.5 mm high (measured without the horns). Male is characterised by three horns on the pronotum: two outer horns are relatively slender, 5.5 mm long, with a short protrusion in the middle. As in the described male, the outer horns are curved towards each other. The small protrusions on the upper side of the larger lateral horns are less developed. The variability of the new species is quite evident, but it repeats regularly according to the size of the adults. The middle horn does not have a raised carina on its ventral area, even in well-developed males. Pronotal surface is smooth and shiny, except for punctate basal and dorsal area of outer horns.

Elytra shaped as in Fig. 4, 1–2. Elytral surface covered with longitudinal striae of variable intensity and depth, but always sharply delimited from intervals and possessing distinct microstructure consisting of denser punctures inside the striae. The intervals between the striae are irregularly covered with extremely fine, microscopic wrinkles (Fig. 5, 1).

Protibiae (Fig. 3, 3) have coarse and blunter spines on the outer side. There is no elongated radial groove above the tibial spines on the upper surface facing the joint.

Abdomen. The ventrites are black-blue, with fine hair-like setae.

Genitalia (Fig. 3, 2). The aedeagus of the male holotype is 2.8 mm long, the shape is obvious from Fig. 3,2.

Figure 1. Two species of *Typhaeus*, habitus, dorsal view. **1** – *T. bubeniki* sp. nov., ♀, paratypus. **2** – *T. bubeniki* sp. nov., ♂, holotype. **3** – *T. typhoeus*, ♂, Cantabria, Cabuérniga-environs, Spain (AWHS).

Characters of female (Fig. 1, 1). Pronotum in female is entirely coarsely punctate and matt. It has about 3 mm long horizontal ridge in the middle of the anterior margin of the pronotum, above which there is a convex structure divided by a fine and shallow groove. These two rounded areas are distinctly dotted. On either side of the ridge there are two small horns 0.5 mm in size, one above the other. The upper two protrusions are level with the ridge and the other two are lower, at the edge of the pronotum near the head. They are not directed straightforward but are deflected to the sides at an angle of about 10°. When viewed from the front, these two small horns overlap on both sides. The conical end of the female vertex-frons with clypeus pointing towards the labrum is curved at the lateral edges.

Elytra. The striae on the female elytra (Fig. 1, 1) and their microstructure are identical with the description and illustrations of the male holotype (as in, Fig. 4, 1–2, Fig. 5, 1).

Protibiae in female (visible in Fig. 1, 1) have the same shape as in the male holotype described above and illustrated in Fig. 3, 3).

Overall habitus of males and females. The surface coloration is predominantly black, with a slight bluish tinge in some specimens.

Figure 2. Two species of *Typhaeus*, head part showing vertex, frons, clypeus and labrum. **1** – *T. bubeniki* sp. nov., ♂, holotype. **2** – *T. typhoeus*, ♂, Cantabria, Cabuérniga-environs, Spain (AWHS).

Variability. The variability of the new species is quite pronounced and as a rule, the characters are generally confined to the size of adults. Body length 16–21 mm. The long outer horns of males are 2.0–6.5 mm long.

Differential diagnosis

Typhaeus bubeniki sp. nov. has a noticeably smaller width and height of the labrum (Fig. 2, 1) than *T. typhoeus*. The labrum is also clearly thicker. The narrow anterior margin of labrum in the new species is truncate, almost flat; labral surface is covered with foveae and fine punctures. In contrast, the anterior labral margin of *T. typhoeus* (Fig. 2, 2) is slightly sinuous and in lateral view the labrum is strongly narrowed towards its front edge, and its surface is covered with larger foveae and punctures. Thus, overall appearance of the labrum of *T. typhoeus* is much larger and more arched on the sides than that of *T. bubeniki* sp. nov.

Figure 3. Two species of *Typhaeus*. **1–3** – *Typhaeus bubeniki* sp. nov., ♂, holotype: **1** – vertex, frons and clypeus; **2** – dorsal and lateral view of aedeagus; **3** – right protibia, dorsal view. **4–6** – *Typhaeus typhoeus*, ♂, Cantabria, Cabuérniga-environs, Spain (AWHS): **4** – vertex, frons and clypeus; **5** – dorsal and lateral view of aedeagus. **6** – right protibia, dorsal view.

The elytra of *Typhaeus bubeniki* sp. nov. are striate in such a way that the striae lack inner fine wavy wrinkles and are more densely dotted inside; the convex intervals between the striae are more densely irregularly covered with microscopic, mostly transverse wrinkles which are visible to the naked eye, while the wrinkles are sparser and mostly irregularly longitudinal in *T. typhoeus*. Moreover, the punctures in *T. bubeniki* sp. nov. do not interlope the intervals as it is often the case in *T. typhoeus*. The difference is clearly recognisable when using a magnifying glass (compare the details in Fig. 5, 1 with Fig. 5, 2).

The legs of *T. bubeniki* sp. nov. have more robust protibiae with blunter spines (Fig. 3, 3), while the protibiae of *Typhaeus typhoeus* (Fig. 3, 6) are slimmer and sharper; after examining a number of specimens, the differences appeared consistent. In addition, *T. typhoeus* has a wide sulcus on the outer surface of the protibiae, extending to the joint.

The length of lateral horns in males is highly variable in both species (Fig. 1, 2–3). However, the outer horns of males in *T. bubeniki* sp. nov. (Fig. 1, 2) are curved inward, while those in *T. typhoeus* are generally more robust and straighter (Fig. 1, 3); moreover, the new species has the surface of the outer horns more distinctly punctate near their base and dorsally, while the surface of the outer horns is generally almost smooth in *T. typhoeus*. The middle horn in well-developed males of *T. typhoeus* have a distinct carina on its ventral side. In contrast, even in large, well-developed males of *T. bubeniki* sp. nov., this carina is entirely absent. The ventral body side possesses no significant differences between the two species. The male aedeagi of both species show clear differences in dorsal and lateral view (compare Fig. 3, 2 for *T. bubeniki* sp. nov., with Fig. 3, 5 in the same figure for *T. typhoeus*).

Figure 4. Two species of *Typhaeus*. 1–4 – left elytron: 1–2 – *Typhaeus bubeniki* sp. nov.: 1 – ♂, holotype; 2 – ♂, paratype. 3–4 – *Typhaeus typhoeus*, ♂, Cantabria, Cabuérniga environs, Spain, (AWHS).

Differences between females of *Typhaeus typhoeus* and *T. bubeniki* sp. nov. The female of *Typhaeus typhoeus* has a more pronounced and distinct bulge on the pronotum above the horizontal edge, divided by a deeper groove. These areas are very shiny and almost without dots (pits). The difference in this part of the pronotum is clearly visible under a magnifying

glass (4x) in the female *T. bubeniki* sp. nov. The small horns on the sides of the female *T. bubeniki* sp. nov. are in the same line (Fig. 1, 1). In *T. typhoeus*, the lower horns point more to the sides, while the upper horns point towards each other and therefore do not form a line. This is clearly visible when viewed from the front of the pronotum. The striae on the elytra of the female and male in *T. bubeniki* sp. nov. are consistent and thus differing from *T. typhoeus*. This difference is described in the holotype *Typhaeus bubeniki* sp. nov. above.

1

2

Figure 5. Two species of *Typhaeus*, detail of elytral surface: **1** – *Typhaeus bubeniki* sp. nov., ♂ paratype. **2** – *Typhaeus typhoeus*, ♂, Cantabria, Cabuérniga environs, Spain, (AWHS).

Figure 6. *Typhaeus typhoeus*, ♂ (LINN 3321), male lectotype of *Scarabaeus typhoeus* Linnaeus, 1758, designated by Landin (1956). Adopted from LINN online database.

On type specimens of *Typhaeus typhoeus*

In the very brief original description by Linnaeus (1758), as *Scarabaeus typhoeus*, he does not mention a number of specimens. According to the Linnean Society (LINN) online database, there are several specimens of this species. As discussed by Landin (1956) it is not clear if all the specimens of taxa described by Linnaeus and deposited in LINN come from his own collection and if all are types. As Linnaeus and other historical authors did not provide their type specimens by a label “type”, it was sometimes difficult to recognize them clearly. Nevertheless, as noted by Landin (1956), among the possible type specimens of taxa listed by him, judging also from shape of pins, specimens of two of the LINN taxa, just of *S. typhoeus* and *S. lunaris*, are most probably authentic. The male specimen (now LINN 3321), with its original labels by Linnaeus, with also “6” on one of its two labels, was considered by Landin (1956) to be the original type specimen of *S. typhoeus*. The same specimen was consequently listed as a lectotype by Schoolmeesters (2025), based on the lectotype designation by Landin (1956). Such treatment by Landin in 1956 is considered justified lectotype designation according to Art. 74.6. (ICZN 1999), although there is no lectotype label in LINN (Andrea Deneau, LINN digital assets manager, *pers. com.*). See Fig. 6 here, showing the male lectotype (LINN 3321) adopted from the LINN online database.

Genetic sequence comparison

sequence difference 1.95%

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CLUSTAL format alignment by MAFFT (v7.511)

TtypIN27  aacattatatttcttatttggatcgtgagcaggaatagttggaacatcactaagaatttt
TbubIN28  aacattatatttcttatttggatcgtgagcaggaataattggaacatcactaagaatttt
*****_*****

TtypIN27  aattcgagctgaattaggaatccgggatctttaattggagatgaccaaatttttaatgt
TbubIN28  aattcgagctgaattaggaatccgggatctttaattggagatgaccaaatttttaatgt
*****

TtypIN27  aattgttacagctcatgcttttgttataattttttttagttatacctattttaattgg
TbubIN28  aattgttacagctcatgcttttgttataattttttttagttatacctattttaattgg
*****

TtypIN27  gggattcgaaattgattagtgaccttaataattaggggcacctgatatagcattcccacg
TbubIN28  aggattcgaaattgattagtgaccttaataattaggggcacctgatatagcattcccacg
_******_*****

TtypIN27  aataaataatataagattttgattacttccctcactaactcttttattaataagaag
TbubIN28  aataaataatataagattttgattacttccccctcactaactcttttattaataagaag
*****_*****

TtypIN27  attagtagaaagaggagcaggaacagggtgaactgtttacccccctcttcagcaaatat
TbubIN28  attagtagaaagaggggcaggaacaggatgaactgtttacccccctcttcagcaaatat
*****_******_******

TtypIN27  tgcccatagaggagcatctgttgacttagctatttttcccttcatttagcgggaatttc
TbubIN28  tgcccatagaggagcatctgttgacttagctatttttcccttcatttagcgggaatttc
*****

TtypIN27  ttcaattttaggagcagtgaaattttattgctactgttattaatgcatcaacaggaat
TbubIN28  ctcaattttaggagcagtgaaattttattgctactgttattaatgcatcaacaggaat
_******_******

TtypIN27  aacctttgatcgcatacccttatttgtttgagcagtagtattaactgctttattattact
TbubIN28  aacctttgatcgcatacccttatttgtttgagcagtagtattaactgctttattattact
*****

TtypIN27  tttatctctaccagtattagctggggcaattacaatattattaacagatcgaattttaa
TbubIN28  tttatctctaccagtattagctggggcaattacaatattattaacagatcgaattttaa
*****_*

TtypIN27  tacctcttttttgaccctgcaggaggaggatcctattttataccaacatttattt
TbubIN28  tacctcttttttgaccctgcaggaggaggatcctattttataccaacatttattt
*****_******

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Figure 7. Genetic analysis. Genetic sequence comparison: TtypIN27–*Typhaeus typhoeus* ♂, Cantabria, Cabuérniga-env., Spain, leg. J. Navarro (AWHS). TbubIN28–*Typhaeus bubeniki* sp.nov., holotype, ♂, Murcia, Cañada de la Cruz, Spain, leg. Bubeník and Wrzecionko (AWHS). Performed by D. Kaspřák on November 24, 2025, Dekódovna laboratory, Havířov, Czech Republic.

Comparative specimens. *Typhaeus typhoeus*: 5 ♂♂ and 3 ♀♀ – Spain: Cantabria, Cabuérniga-env. (leg. J. Navarro 2.6.1988) – 1 ♂, 21 mm long (Fig. 1, 3): Spain, Cantabria, Cabuérniga (AWHS).

6 ♂♂ and 4 ♀♀ – Spain, Ávila – El Castañar, El Tiemblo-env. (leg. J. Urbano 10.10.2009). 4 ♂♂ and 2 ♀♀ – Morocco: Rif Mts. Ketama, 1500 m, Bab Beret-env. (leg. A. Wrzecionko 24.6.2012). 1 ♂ – Czech Republic: Bohemia, vicinity of Mimoň (leg. L. Bartůněk 12.6.1952)

2 males and 1 ♀ – Czech Republic: Bohemia, Hřensko, Mezní Louka (leg. V. Týr 20 October 2013). All in BBFM and AWHS.

Figure 8. *Typhaeus typhoeus*, recorded occurrence during the years 1793–2025 (adopted from: www.gbif.org, Edinburgh, England).

Figure 9. *Typhaeus bubeniki* sp. nov., recorded occurrence during the years 2022–2025.

Biology and distribution.

Typhaeus bubeniki sp. nov. is currently known only from the type locality in the province of Murcia, in the Cañada de la Cruz area of Spain (Fig.9).

Similar to *Typhaeus typhoeus*, the new species occurs in meadows and can also be found on the edges of open forests. However, *T. typhoeus* is known from other areas of Spain, see its distribution map. (Fig. 8).

These locations are not particularly rich in sandy soil. Unfortunately, wild meadows in Spain are often destroyed and gradually planted with lavender. In locations where *T. bubeniki* sp. nov. occurs (Fig. 10) in very stony soil at an altitude of 1600–1700 m, almond orchards have also been observed. *T. bubeniki* sp. nov. digs shallow tunnels, probably due to the large amount of stones deep in the soil. The new species does not occur in open pine forests with sandy soils. *T. typhoeus* has not been recorded in the area where *T. bubeniki* sp. nov. occurs.

Etymology. The new species is named in honour of Boris Bubeník, M.D., from Frýdek-Místek in Silesia, Czech Republic, one of the collectors of new species.

Figure 10. *Typhaeus bubeniki* sp. nov. Type locality, Surroundings of Cañada de la Cruz, Murcia, Spain.

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